

Does Intelligence Matters in Teaching? Exploring the Impact of Teachers Intelligence on Teaching Pedagogies of Secondary School Science Teachers

Rani Gul, Muhammad Talat, Majid Mumtaz, Lubna Shaheen

Article Info

Article History

Received:
December 30, 2020

Accepted:
March 30, 2021

Keywords :

Capacity Enhancement,
Individual Differences,
Intellectual Strength,
Students' Achievements,
Teaching Pedagogies.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.4647944

Abstract

Intellectual strengths of the teachers can have a robust impact on their teaching pedagogies. This study illuminates the nine multiple intelligences and its impact on the teaching pedagogies of the science teachers teaching at secondary schools. Data were collected using two different questionnaires from 252 male and female science teachers, sampled through proportionate random sampling technique, from urban and rural areas of district Peshawar. Findings revealed significant gender differences in visual and kinesthetic intelligences and a consistently positive effect ($r = +.581$) of science teachers' multiple intelligences on their teaching pedagogies was also observed. The study suggests that teacher education institutes, teaching curriculum developers, policymakers may concentrate on secondary school science teachers' capacity enhancement in line with their multiple intelligences to enhance their teaching skills and make teaching more effective.

Introduction

Research studies on the contribution of teachers to teach and students to learn science remained a high area of interest in past decades (Gore, 2017). Quality of education is basically grounded in the quality of teaching which is directly linked with academic credentials and professional experiences of the teachers (Bowles, Hattie, Dinham, Scull, & Clinton, 2014). How science teachers are equipped with the professional knowledge and skills to ensure that teaching and curriculum encounter the 21st-century global challenges, is the key attention of the day.

To learn science collaboratively and meaningfully, it is necessary for secondary school students to develop high level critical and coherent thinking underpinned with strong decisive and interpersonal skills, executive and cooperative abilities, empathetic understanding of self and other, and commitment towards personal and social responsibility (Gul, R., & Reba, A. 2017). To inculcate such abilities in students, science teachers themselves have to strengthen their own different intellectual strength (Gul, R., Khan, S. S., Mazhar, S., & Tahir, T. 2020).

This study aims to investigate the different intellectual strengths of secondary school science teachers (SST) and the impact of their intellectual strengths on their teaching pedagogies. The study is significant because teachers are the most important pillars in building a productive learning environment and they perform a significant role in the classroom. Modification and alteration in teaching science are required to enhance students' performance and groom their overall personality. Today the biggest factor in deteriorating the quality of education is the quality of teaching science subjects (Kazmi, 2016). The research found that teachers styles of teaching have a foretelling effect on students learning (Sulaiman, Abdurahman, & Rahim, 2010). It has also been reported that in secondary school classrooms', the most practices instructional pedagogies are teachers centered, which do not boost students critical thinking, instead compelled students towards cramming in order to get high marks in board examinations (Gul, R., & Rafique, M. 2017).

The study is substantial because it creates awareness to the school teachers that all their students may not be successful in learning by adopting only certain traditional methods of teaching. By employing the teaching pedagogies which are based on the intellectual needs of the teachers and students can guide students towards conceptual understanding and creative learning (Gul, R., Kanwal, S., & Khan, S. S. 2020). Additionally, this may assist science teachers and students to identify and utilize their intellectual abilities in teaching (Gul, R., & Reba, A. 2017). Teachers fully equipped with the latest teaching pedagogies play a key role in the overall success of the academic and educational performance of the students (Gul, R., & Muhammad, R. 2017).

Theoretical framework

The study investigated how secondary school science teachers can use their own intellectual strengths in suggesting a variety of student's centred instructional techniques suitable to nourish their critical, social and executive abilities. To measure the different intelligences, this study has been grounded on Howard Gardner Multiple intelligence theory (1983). This theory provides a wide-ranging basis for different intellectual potentials, a human being may possess. This theory present that every human being has nine multiple intelligences and if the proper environment is provided, these intelligences can be enhanced and strengthen. These intelligences included Linguistics Spatial-Visual, Kinesthetic, Logical-Mathematical, Musical, Interpersonal Naturalistic, Existentialistic and Intrapersonal Intelligences (Checkley, 1997; Gardner & Hatch, 1989).

i: Linguistic/Verbal Intelligence is responsive to language structure, words and its various shades of meanings in varying text and context. The teaching pedagogies included Teaching in group discussion, storytelling, books provision to students and providing a public speaking opportunity to students (Weber, 2006).

ii: Logical /Mathematical Intelligence, one can understand simple numerical patterns –addition, division, multiplication, subtraction, width, breadth-measurement of length etc. The teaching pedagogies included logical questions quizzes, coherent thinking, cause and effect relationship, and building connection among topics (Armstrong, 2009).

iii: Visual Intelligence: this intelligence includes understanding charts and maps, visualizing things, visual demos, drawing and sketching etc. Teaching pedagogies included material sketching and drawing, visualizing content, demonstration of the concept by creating a model, and showing videos (Weber, 2006).

iv: Kinesthetic/Bodily Intelligence helps in physical expressions –motor skills involving sports activity. The teaching pedagogies included role-play, showing gesture, and postures, experiments, seeing and touching the objects (Armstrong, 2009).

v: Interpersonal Intelligence improves communication skills to relate to others and understand their feelings. The teaching pedagogies included characterizing and personalizing the topics, sharing question answers, interaction, and discussion with other students, cooperative work (Armstrong, 2009).

vi: The Musical /Rhythmical Intelligence is conscious to recognize fall and rise in sounds, the low and high pitch, resonance, melody, tone, and rhythm in the environment. The teaching pedagogies included playing background sounds or music related to a specific topic, teaching concepts in a musical tune, using number games books, using recorded music, games of word pattern (Armstrong, 2009).

vii: The Intrapersonal Intelligence is the state of being able to grip one's self-emotions and physical sensation with the outer environment. The teaching pedagogies included expressing feelings and opinions, using emotions, making choice in learning activities, personal connections (Armstrong, 2009).

viii: The Naturalistic Intelligence enables one to understand 'the Nature' and its ways to human beings, its phenomenon and its moods to our environment. The teaching pedagogies included bringing natural objects into the class, teaching in a natural setting, making projects and crafts of natural materials, learning through senses and observation (Armstrong, 2009).

ix: while the Existential Intelligence makes know about the shapes and existence of things around us (H. Gardner, 2004). The teaching pedagogies included providing opportunities for students preferred topics, arranging talk of a resource person for additional information, allowing students to present the learned things in new ways (Weber, 2006).

Theory of Multiple Intelligence (MI) defined intelligence as a group of different individuals collaborating to perform a mission. On the one hand, the theory studies and tests an individual's intellectual capacity and on the other, it reviews the processes and methods involved in the acquisition of information and learning. It also paved the way for the use of different teaching strategies, because each form of multiple intelligence has a variety of suitable teaching strategies. Through using these techniques teachers can improve student in-class success (Armstrong, 1999). The central point of this theory is that teachers should express knowledge in such a way as to clear and convenient to students' intellect (Gul, R., Khan, S. S., & Akhtar, S. 2020).

Literature shows that ample of researchers have studied and approved the implementation of the teaching pedagogies' in alignment to students and teachers' multiple intelligences enhance the performance of the students (Denig, 2004; Ayub, A., Gul, R., Malik, M., Sharjeel, Y. M., Rauf, B. M. 2021; Ozdener & Ozcuban, 2004; Thompson & Thornton, 2002). Previous researchers on MI theory (Abaci, 2007; Durmaz, 2005; Elibol, 2000; Katranci & Bozkus, 2014; Ozdermir, Guneyesu, & Tekkaya, 2006; Puduk & Baran, 2009), reflecting variables of gender, in which interpersonal, naturalistic and visual intelligence presented a significant effect on teaching pedagogies. While, intrapersonal, logical/mathematical, verbal/linguistics, bodily/kinesthetic, musical variables showed no significant effect on teaching pedagogies.

Research Questions

- What are the preferred teaching pedagogies of male and female science teachers teaching at secondary schools?
- When a gender-based distribution is applied, how these science teachers differ in their levels of multiple intelligences?

- To what extent science teachers' nine multiple intelligence affect their preferred teaching pedagogies?

Review of Related Literature

Propounded by Gardner way back in 1983, the Multiple Intelligence (MI) is considered as one of the recent theories that could be used to examine and assess one's mental capabilities along with methods and process of acquiring knowledge and learning. Sherman (2001); Mills (2001); Willis and Johnson (2001) studies found that teaching with MI produced much creativity and interest in the class than rote memorization. In the study of Temur (2007), the results presented more mathematical comprehension in students who studied with MIT as compared to the lecture method classroom (Ozdermir et al., 2006).

Some of the research studies (Christison, 1996; Serin et al., 2009) has shown no gender differences in term of logical, intrapersonal, kinesthetic and visual intelligence among college students. While some studies on intelligences reflecting gender variable investigated by Abaci (2007); Tas (2007); Sulim (2012); Ucak, Bag, and Usak (2006) found that visual, naturalistic and interpersonal variables have shown a momentous effect on instructional pedagogies and preferences. While intrapersonal, linguistic, kinesthetic, musical, and mathematical variables shown no significant effect on teaching pedagogies. Mujahid (2008) reported in his research that logical and intrapersonal intelligence pedagogies varies. The same findings were reported by Highland, McNally, and Peart (1999) and Al-Khatib and Hamza (2009) research findings, who suggested that in devising teaching pedagogies, the different intellectual potentials of the students and teachers must be kept in mind specifically in logical, visual, and kinesthetic intelligence as theses intelligence effect has been highly reported by previous studies. In another study (Serin et al., 2009), it was found that logical, interpersonal, spatial/visual intelligence has had a great association with the teaching pedagogies of the elementary school teachers.

The findings of another study Douglas, Burton, and Reese-Durham (2008) highlighted that these pedagogies have practical implications for students and classroom practices, are scrutinized with logical and visual intelligence (Yin, Lee, & Zhang, 2013). In the study of Coskunganullu (1998), the results presented a great effect of logical, linguistics and spatial Intelligence of the class fifth students in the subjects of sciences. Students and teachers both showed positive perspectives about these intelligences (Gul, R., Ayub, A., Mazhar, S., Uddin, S., S., Khanum, M. 2021). In an experimental study in METU Ankara College Turkey, Akbas (2004),_concluded that visual, logical, kinesthetics and linguistics, instructions were effective than the traditional method of teaching. Similarly, Kornhaber et al. (2004) reported. Positive associations between the use of intelligence in teaching pedagogies and improvements in student behaviours, students standardized test scores (Ayub, A., Gul, R., Malik, M., Sharjeel, Y. M., Rauf, B. M. 2021), high rate of parents' participation, motivation (Bukhari, S. K. U. S., Gul, R., Bashir, T., Zakir, S., & Javed, T. 2021), learning, and social adjustment to teach disabled students (Hickey, 2004).

Armstrong (1999) in his book concluded that multiple intelligence theory facilitates teachers with diverse teaching pedagogies which can fulfil different learning needs of the learners and can identify and uplift their hidden potentials.

Methodology

Research Design and Participants:

The study used descriptive survey research in which two separate questionnaires (Multiple intelligence and teaching pedagogies) are administered to secondary school science teachers. According to Borg (2015) Descriptive survey research is considered an appropriate choice when not much is known about the topic and the researcher aims to identify the characteristics, trends, categories and correlations while Questionnaire is considered a more valid tool for gathering information faster than any other means (Borg, 2015, pp. 10-11).

For this descriptive research, 252 secondary school teachers are taken as a sample with a ratio of 146 males and 106 females, proportionally selected (35 % of the whole population) from district Peshawar (urban and rural area), Pakhtunkhwa. Thus, 73 male (50%) and 53 female (50%) from the urban area and 73 male (50%) and 53 female (50%) take part from the rural area. The overall ratio of the participants from rural and urban remained the same, However, the ratio of the male participants stands dominant in the study. Participants' confidentiality is maintained during the entire process of compiling this write up.

Measures

For gathering data from Secondary School Teachers, two separate questionnaires were used. The first questionnaire was used to assess Secondary School Teachers' rates of nine different intelligences. The other questionnaire having thirty-six pedagogies was administered to collect data on teachers' most preferred pedagogies in their mathematics and science classrooms.

1: Questionnaire on Multiple Intelligence assessment:

The questionnaire of multiple intelligence measure nine intelligences of the participants. For help, The Ellen Weber (1999) multiple intelligence questionnaire was consulted. Research studies (e.g. Armstrong, 1999; Silver, 1997) affirms the appropriateness of this tool for multiple intelligences assessment. There were 40 items for eight intelligence in the original MI inventory (Weber, 1999), and the participants were requested to pick at least 15 statements which were close to their opinions.

In the present analysis, the evaluation was modified to obtain a numerical score for each of the nine intelligences, five statements for nine kinds of intelligence were made on Likert scale (4-points) with “4” for “Strongly Agree, “3” for “Agree, “2” for Disagree and “1” for “Strongly Disagree” to rate all 45-items of the questionnaire. MI questionnaire shed light on Question 2 of the Study.

2: Teaching Pedagogies Questionnaire

The questionnaire contains thirty-six (36) pedagogies which teachers may use to provide instruction using nine multiple intelligences. The 36 items on the questionnaire were rated on Likert Scale (4-point) which ranked with "1" for “Rarely”, "2" for “Sometimes”, "3" for “Frequently” and "4" for “Always”.

Teaching pedagogies used in this questionnaire were taken from the multiple-intelligence literature. The questionnaire on teaching methods shed some light on research question 1.

The validity of the instruments: questionnaire for multiple intelligences are comprised of nine constructs, each construct had further five items each. These nine constructs were confirmed using the scree plot and the figure below shows nine-factor models that confirm that the questionnaire is valid and has nine constructs. The Cronbach's alpha after piloting of MI questionnaire was found .902 and for teaching pedagogies, it was .888.

Results

Gender and school location of The Participants

Participants were asked to mention their gender (Male or Female) and write the school location (Urban or Rural) on the questionnaire; frequency distribution evaluated the performance of the participants ' responses. The results of the study are set out in Table-1.

Table-1 reveals that with the ratio of (F: 73) male participated in the study from both urban and rural area. Similarly female with a ratio of (F: 53) participated from both urban and rural area. Hence both gender participation percentage was 50:50 and that overall ratio of the participants from rural and urban remained the same, However, in both genders, the ratio of the male participants stands dominant in the study as compared to female.

Research Question One: What are the preferred teaching pedagogies of male and female science teachers teaching at secondary schools?

The mean of responses to the questionnaire on teaching pedagogies was summed up according to their nine areas. The results were analyzed using descriptive statistics.

Descriptive Results: Table-2 shows the outcomes of the descriptive analysis for all teaching pedagogies preferred by science teachers.

In Table-2, the results show that the mean of Logical Pedagogy (M= 3.20, SD = .469) is found to be at top among all pedagogies, while the mean of musical pedagogy (M = 1.73, SD = .779) observed at low level. The findings also show that the mean observed intrapersonal pedagogy is M= 2. 99 with SD = .590, followed by

interpersonal pedagogies ($M = 2.99$, $SD = .590$), intrapersonal pedagogies ($M = 2.99$ with $SD = .590$), kinesthetic pedagogies ($M = 2.87$, $SD = .567$), linguistic pedagogies ($M = 2.7$, $SD = .599$), existential pedagogies ($M = 2.67$, $SD = .633$), naturalistic pedagogies ($M = 2.40$, $SD = .752$) and visual pedagogies ($M = 2.40$, $SD = .716$).

T-Test Results: To examine the difference between male and female participants' preferences in using different teaching pedagogies, t-test was used and results are given in table-3.

Table-3 illustrates that female and male are not significantly differ in the level of linguistics pedagogies, logical pedagogies, naturalistic pedagogies, visual pedagogies, kinesthetic pedagogies, musical pedagogies, naturalistic pedagogies and intrapersonal pedagogies, except for existentialistic pedagogies with ($t = 2.265$, $p = .024$) and interpersonal pedagogies with ($t = -2.032$, $p = .043$) where a significant gender difference is observed and male are found dominant in using these two teaching pedagogies.

Research Question Two: When a gender-based distribution is applied, how these science teachers differ in their levels of multiple intelligences?

The mean of responses on MI questionnaire is summed up and divided by the total number of statements. Descriptive statistics were applied to analyze the scores for each of the nine constraints of MI (table-4), while T-test was used to find out gender difference in the levels of MI (table-5).

Descriptive Results: Table-4 show existentialistic intelligence ($M = 3.20$, $SD = .514$) at the highest level, accompanied by other intelligences like linguistic with ($M = 3.10$, $SD = .420$) and interpersonal ($M = 3.10$, with $SD = .475$). Similarly visual with ($M = 3.09$, and $SD = .528$), naturalistic with ($M = 3.08$ and $SD = .486$), logical with ($M = 3.02$, and $SD = .494$), intrapersonal with ($M = 2.91$, $SD = .564$), were observed. But on the other hand, the lowest mean was observed for musical with ($M = 2.72$, $SD = .530$), and kinesthetic intelligence with ($M = 2.70$, $SD = .478$).

Independent Sample t-test Results: In table-5, results of the independent sample t-test ($\alpha = .05$) indicates that , females illustrates significant high level of visual intelligence with ($t = -2.59$, $p = .01$), musical intelligence with ($t = -2.34$, $p = .019$), and kinesthetic with ($t = -2.50$, $p = .013$) as compared to male while no significant gender difference is found in intelligence levels of linguistics with ($t = -.806$, $p = .421$), logical with ($t = .061$, $p = .955$), intrapersonal with ($t = -1.87$, $p = .061$), interpersonal with ($t = 1.92$, $p = .055$), naturalistic with ($t = -.925$, $p = .356$) and existentialistic with ($t = -.967$, $p = .335$).

Research Question Three: To what extent do science teachers nine multiple intelligence leave an effect on their pedagogy.

To examine the effect of different levels of multiple intelligence on their pedagogies, Pearson r correlation coefficient test was applied. Results are presented in table-6.

Data in table 6 predicts that the level of intelligence of linguistic with ($r = +.294$, $p < .05$, two-tailed), logical with ($r = .193$, $p < .05$), visual with ($r = +.299$, $p < .05$), musical with ($r = +.358$, $p < .05$), kinesthetic with ($r = +.231$, $p < .05$), interpersonal with ($r = +.273$, $p < .05$), intrapersonal with ($r = +.231$, $p < .05$), naturalistic ($r = +.476$, $p < .05$) and existentialistic with ($r = +.302$, $p < .05$) showed a positive and significant and correlation with their respective pedagogies.

The Pearson correlation coefficient with overall ($r = +.582$, $n = 252$, $p = .000$) value indicated a significant correlation among MI and teaching pedagogies which illustrates that intelligence affects the teaching pedagogies.

Discussion and Conclusion

The study has incorporated multiple intelligence theory, which is widely acknowledged and implemented in developing countries ((Liarakou, Gavrilakis, &Flouri, 2009). The study shed light on different levels of MI of the science teachers and its impact on their teaching pedagogies at district Peshawar.

The findings of the study reveal gender coherence in all teaching pedagogies except in existential teaching pedagogies, which may be attributed to a high degree of academic and professional education of the participants from both genders. The studies of Wilson, Floden, and Ferrini-Mundy (2001) support this claim because they found a strong correlation among the educational level of teachers and teachers' effectiveness. The results are consistent with some other studies (Greenwald, Hedges, and Laine, 1996; & Rivkin and Hanushek, 2007) who evaluated the impact of teacher education and training and found a positive effect on their instruction and performance. The findings are significant because in existing literature no solid empirical research has still been documented gender-based differences in teaching pedagogies of the school teachers.

The findings further reflect that both male and female science teachers possessed different levels of all nine multiple intelligences. The difference in their levels of multiple intelligences illustrates that the results are consistent with Gardner's theory of multiple intelligence. The theory suggests that all individuals possess all kinds of intelligences, although the levels of each intelligence in individuals are different (Gardner, 1983). The results are significant because it not only proves that each individual has distinctive abilities, but it also shows that no individual is feeble-minded, and their weakest intelligences can be improved.

The results further elucidate that in the levels of visual, kinesthetic, and interpersonal intelligence females were stronger than males. The results are supported by the findings of Snyder (1999) and Abdul Aziz (2008), which reported female faculty members a high level of linguistic, kinesthetic, logical, visual, intrapersonal and interpersonal intelligence in comparison to the male. But, the findings are opposed with other findings like McClellan (2006), Asha, Iyer, and Sen (2007), Hanafiyeh (2013) who found no gender difference in the levels of MI except in Linguistic and Musical intelligence. The high level of visual, kinesthetic, and interpersonal intelligence in females as compared to male might be due to social practices and age of the participants because studies affirm that women to a greater extent are more sensitive to the interpersonal communication and likely have strong interpersonal skills and mostly like to remain physically active as compared to male (Tnneen, 1990; wood, 2009). Ali, Suliman, Kareem, and Iqbal (2009) also concluded that social influences may bring gender difference in multiple intelligence.

The results also indicate a significant correlation of teachers' levels of MI with their respective teaching pedagogies. The results are consistent with the results of Serin, Serin, Yavuz and Muhammedzade (2009), who found that the teachers' multiple intelligences have a predictive impact on their instructional strategies. The current results are also very similar to the results of the findings of Sulaiman, Abdurahman and Rahim (2010), which suggest that multiple intelligence rates are strongly associated with their teaching strategies. However, Mujahid (2008) and AlSulim (2012) reported contradiction in the teaching pedagogies of logical and Intrapersonal intelligence while Durmaz (2005) findings revealed the impact of naturalistic, visual and interpersonal intelligence on teaching pedagogies.

The findings are very important as it affirms that the relationship between multiple intelligences and its related teaching methods is very significant in the academic success of the students. The research studies of (Ozdermir, Guneyusu, and Tekkaya, 2006; Serin, Serin, Yavuz, and Muhammedzade, 2009; Walker, 1998 & Sulaiman, Abdurahman, and Rahim, 2010) concluded a strong association of MI and its related teaching pedagogies on students conceptual learning and academic performance.

The current study supports that skills, behaviour, and concepts are developed by conducting activities associated with the intellectual abilities of the students through the use of multiple intelligence areas. To fulfil abilities and needs of the students' concerning learning preferences and their distinctive intelligences, the policymakers and curriculum developers in Pakistan, specifically, in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, need to think on the science teachers' capacity enhancement in alignment to their multiple intellectual domains in compiling standards for teacher education in the coming educational policy 2018-2023, new provincial teacher education curriculum and in-service teachers training manuals, viable enhance their teaching abilities and professional development (Gul, R., Khilji, G. 2021).

Most of the previous studies used seven intelligences whereas this study has taken into consideration all the nine intelligences. The literature witnessed that no previous studies have been conducted in this area in Pakistan, thus findings of the current study illuminate the literature in the area of MI by aligning it with the teaching pedagogies.

The current study recommends further research on the multiple intelligence in line with teaching pedagogies using qualitative and mixed-method approaches for an in-depth understanding of the phenomena.

References

- Akbas, A. (2004). *The Effects of Multiple Intelligences Based Instruction on Sixth Graders Science Achievement and Attitudes Towards Science*. METU. www.bookzz.com database.
- Al Sulim, G. H. (2012). Prediction of the correlation between the strategies of the teaching methods and the Multiple Intelligence of some graduate female students at Imam Mohammad Ibn Saud Islamic University. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 47, 1268-1275.
- Ali, M. S., Suliman, M. I., Kareem, A., & Iqbal, M. (2009). Comparison of gender performance on an intelligence test among medical students. *J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad*, 21(3), 163-165.
- Armstrong, T. (1998). *Awakening genius in the classroom*: ASCD.
- Armstrong, T. (2009). *Multiple intelligences in the classroom*: Ascd.
- Athanases, S. Z., Sanchez, S. L., & Martin, L. M. (2020). Saturate, situate, synthesize: Fostering preservice teachers' conceptual and practical knowledge for learning to lead class discussion. *Teaching and teacher education*, 88, 102970.
- Ayub, A., Gul, R., Malik, M., Sharjeel, Y. M., Rauf, B. M. (2021). Impact of Interactive Pedagogies on Students' Academic Achievement in Mathematics at Elementary School Level in Quetta City, Balochistan. *Ilkogretim Online - Elementary Education Online*, 20 (3): pp. 53-72. <http://ilkogretim-online.org>: 10.17051/ilkonline.2021.03.06
- Barrington, E. (2004). Teaching to student diversity in higher education: How multiple intelligence theory can help. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 9(4), 421-434.

- Bas, G., & Beyhan, Ö. (2010). Effects of Multiple Intelligences Supported Project-Based Learning on Students' Achievement Levels and Attitudes towards English Lesson. *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 2(3), 365-386.
- Bates, I. (1998). The 'empowerment' dimension in the GNVQ: a critical exploration of discourse, pedagogic apparatus and school implementation. *Evaluation & Research in Education*, 12(1), 7-22.
- Berry, B., Hoke, M., & Hirsch, E. (2004). NCLB: Highly qualified teachers-the search for highly qualified teachers. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 85(9), 684.
- Blign, E. K. (2006). *The effect of multiple intelligences-based instruction on ninth graders chemistry achievement and attitudes toward chemistry*. Citeseer.
- Borg, S. (2015). *Teacher cognition and language education: Research and practice*: Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Brualdi, A. C. (1996). Multiple Intelligences: Gardner's Theory. ERIC Digest.
- Bukhari, S. K. U. S., Gul, R., Bashir, T., Zakir, S., & Javed, T. (2021). Exploring managerial skills of Pakistan Public Universities (PPUs) middle managers for campus sustainability. *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, 1-19. doi: 10.1080/20430795.2021.1883985
- Campbell, B. (1994). *The multiple intelligences handbook: Lesson plans and more*: Campbell & Assoc Incorporated.
- Campbell, L., Campbell, B., & Dickinson, D. (1999). *Through multiple intelligences*: Needham Heights, MA: Allyn & Bacon.
- Condis, P., Parks, D., & Soldwedel, R. (2000). *Enhancing Vocabulary and Language Using Multiple Intelligences*. (Master of Arts Action Research Project), Saint Xavier University and SkyLight Professional Development. Available from <http://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED441269.pdf>
- Corcoran, R. P., & Tormey, R. (2013). Does emotional intelligence predict student teachers' performance? *Teaching and teacher education*, 35, 34-42.
- Coskunganullu, R. (1998). The effects of multiple intelligences theory on 5th graders' mathematics ability. *Unpublished masters' thesis, Middle East Technical University, Institute of Social Sci-, Middle East Technical University, Institute of Social Sci-Middle East Technical University, Institute of Social Sciences, Ankara*.
- Diamond, J. (1984). "Normal" extinctions of isolated populations.
- Diaz-Lefebvre, R. (2004). Multiple intelligences, learning for understanding, and creative assessment: Some pieces to the puzzle of learning. *Teachers College Record*, 106(1), 49-57.
- Durmaz, H., & Ozyildirim, H. (2005). To investigate the relationship between science and the chemistry classroom teaching students towards fields with multiple intelligences and attitudes chemistry and success in the Turkish language. *Faculty of Education Journal, Gazi University Kirsehir*, 6(1), 67-76.
- Eisner, E. W. (2004). What does it mean to say a school is doing well. *The curriculum studies reader*, 2, 297-305.
- Fauth, B., Decristan, J., Decker, A.-T., Büttner, G., Hardy, I., Klieme, E., & Kunter, M. (2019). The effects of teacher competence on student outcomes in elementary science education: The mediating role of teaching quality. *Teaching and teacher education*, 86, 102882.
- Gardner, & Moran, S. (2006). The science of multiple intelligences theory: A response to Lynn Waterhouse. *Educational psychologist*, 41(4), 227-232.
- Gardner. (2003). Multiple intelligences after twenty years. *American Educational Research Association, Chicago, Illinois*, 21.
- Goldman, K. D., & Schmalz, K. J. (2003). MIT: "Multiple intelligences tips" for tailored teaching. *Health promotion practice*, 4(2), 87-90.
- Gore, A. (2017). *An Inconvenient Sequel: Truth to Power: Your action handbook to learn the science, find your voice, and help solve the climate crisis*: Rodale.
- Gul, R., & Rafique, M. (2017). Teachers Preferred Approaches towards Multiple Intelligence Teaching: Enhanced Prospects for Teaching Strategies. *Journal of Research & Reflections in Education (JRRE)*, 11(2). pp 197-203.
- Gul, R., & Reba, A. (2017). A Study of Multiple Intelligence and Social Profiles of Secondary School Teachers, Peshawar. *Journal of Applied Environmental and Biological Sciences*, 7(6), 226-235.
- Gul, R., Ayub, A., Mazhar, S., Uddin, S., S., Khanum, M. (2021). Teachers' Perceptions on Students' Cultural and Linguistic Diversity and its Impact on their Approaches towards Culturally Teaching Practices. *TESOL International Journal*, 16 (3.2).
- Gul, R., Kanwal, S., & Khan, S. S. (2020). Preferences of the Teachers in Employing Revised Blooms Taxonomy in their Instructions. *Sir Syed Journal of Education & Social Research*, 3(2), 258-266. Doi: 139- Article Text-1546-2-10-20200702.pdf
- Gul, R., Khan, S. S., & Akhtar, S. (2020). Organizational Politics as Antecedent of Stress in Public Sector Universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. *International Review of Management and Business Research*, 9(2), 150-161. Doi:10.30543/9-2(2020)-11 Link: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/228237475.pdf>

- Gul, R., Khan, S. S., Mazhar, S., & Tahir, T. (2020). Influence of Logical and Spatial Intelligence on Teaching Pedagogies of Secondary School Teachers. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 8(6), 01-09. <https://doi.org/10.18510/hssr.2020.861>
- Gul, R., Khilji, G. (2021). Exploring the need for a responsive school curriculum to cope with the Covid-19 pandemic in Pakistan. *Prospects*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11125-020-09540-8>.
- Hoerr, T. (2002). Applying MI in schools. *New horizons for learning*.
- Hole, Y., & Snehal, P. & Bhaskar, M. (2019). Porter's five forces model: gives you a competitive advantage. *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control System*, 11 (4), 1436-1448.
- Kornhaber, M. L., Fierros, E. G., & Veenema, S. A. (2004). *Multiple intelligences: Best ideas from research and practice*: Allyn & Bacon.
- Lazear, D. (2000). *The Intelligent Curriculum: Using Multiple Intelligences To Develop Your Students' Full Potential*: ERIC.
- Liarakou, G., Gavrilakis, C., & Flouri, E. (2009). Secondary school teachers' knowledge and attitudes towards renewable energy sources. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 18(2), 120-129.
- Mettetal, G., Jordan, C., & Harper, S. (1997). Attitudes toward a multiple intelligences curriculum. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 91(2), 115-122.
- Mills, S. (2001). The role of musical intelligence in a multiple intelligences focused elementary school. *International Journal of Education & the Arts*, 2(4).
- Mujahid, F. A. (2008). The Effectiveness of The Proposed Program for The Teaching of History in the Light of The Theory of Multiple Intelligences to Develop Historical Thinking Skills in the First Row of Lower Secondary Pupils. *Reading and knowledge Magazine*, 122-154.
- Noble, T. (2004). Integrating the revised Bloom's taxonomy with multiple intelligences: A planning tool for curriculum differentiation. *Teachers College Record*, 106(1), 193-211.
- Olson, L. (1988). Children flourish here. *Education Week*, 1(18), 18-19.
- Olson, R. E., McKenzie, J., Mills, K. A., Patulny, R., Bellocchi, A., & Caristo, F. (2019). Gendered emotion management and teacher outcomes in secondary school teaching: A review. *Teaching and teacher education*, 80, 128-144.
- Ozdermir, P. i., Guneyusu, S., & Tekkaya, C. (2006). Enhancing learning through. *Journal of Biological Education*, 40(2), 74-78.
- Patterson, M. M., Kravchenko, N., Chen-Bouck, L., & Kelley, J. A. (2016). General and domain-specific beliefs about intelligence, ability, and effort among preservice and practicing teachers. *Teaching and teacher education*, 59, 180-190.
- Serin, N. B., Serin, O., Yavuz, M. A., & Muhammedzade, B. (2009). The relationship between the primary teachers' teaching strategies and their strengths in multiple intelligences (Their multiple intelligence types) (Sampling: Izmir and Lefkosa). *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 1(1), 708-712. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2009.01.124>
- Sherman, L. (2001). Howard Gardner's multiple intelligences. *Oxford, OH: Miami University*. Retrieved November 8, 2014.
- Shore, J. R. (2004). Teacher Education and Multiple Intelligences: A Case Study of Multiple Intelligences and Teacher Efficacy in Two Teacher Preparation Courses. *Teachers College Record*, 106(1), 112-139.
- Silver, H. F., Strong, R. W., & Perini, M. J. (2000). *So each may learn: Integrating learning styles and multiple intelligences*: ERIC.
- Silver, H., Strong, R., & Perini, M. (1997). Integrating Learning Styles and Multiple Intelligences. *Educational Leadership*, 55(1), 22-27.
- Sulaiman, T., Abdurahman, A. R., & Rahim, S. S. A. (2010). Teaching strategies based on multiple intelligences theory among science and mathematics secondary school teachers. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 8, 512-518.
- Temur, O. D. (2007). The Effects of Teaching Activities Prepared According to the Multiple Intelligence Theory on Mathematics Achievements and Permanence of Information Learned by 4th Grade Students. *International Journal of Environmental and Science Education*, 2(4), 86-91.
- Weber, E. (1999). *Student assessment that works: A practical approach*: Allyn and Bacon.
- Whitaker, D. L. (2002). *Multiple Intelligences & After-school Environments: Keeping All Children in Mind*: School-Age Notes.
- Willis, J. K., & Johnson, A. N. (2001). Multiply with MI: Using multiple intelligences to master multiplication. *Teaching Children Mathematics*, 7(5), 260.
- Wilson, S. M., Floden, R. E., & Ferrini-Mundy, J. (2001). *Teacher Preparation Research: Current Knowledge, Gaps, and Recommendations: a Research Report Prepared for the US Department of Education and the Office for Educational Research and Improvement, February 2001*: Center for the Study of Teaching and Policy.

- Xie, J., & Lin, R. (2009). Research on multiple intelligences teaching and assessment. *Asian journal of management and humanity sciences*, 4(2-3), 106-124.
- Yalmanci, S. G., & Gozum, A. (2013). The effects of multiple intelligence theory based teaching on students' achievement and retention of knowledge (example of the enzymes subject). *International Journal on New Trends in Education and Their Implications*, 4(3), 27-36.
- Yin, H., Huang, S., & Lee, J. C. K. (2017). Choose your strategy wisely: Examining the relationships between emotional labor in teaching and teacher efficacy in Hong Kong primary schools. *Teaching and teacher education*, 66, 127-136.
- Yin, H.-b., Lee, J. C. K., & Zhang, Z.-h. (2013). Exploring the relationship among teachers' emotional intelligence, emotional labor strategies and teaching satisfaction. *Teaching and teacher education*, 35, 137-145.

Author Information

Dr Rani Gul

Assistant Professor, Department of Education,
University of Malakand, Chakdara, Pakistan.

Muhammad Talat

Lecturer Department of Education University of
Loralai

Majid Mumtaz

Assistant professor in Urdu University of Kotli Azad
Jammu and Kashmir

Lubna Shaheen

PhD scholar (university of Malaya, Malaysia)
Designation: SST (General) Quetta, Govt. of
Balochistan
